

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11500411>

THE BASIC PRINCIPLES OF GOOD CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

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ANNOTATION

In this article, explain effective classroom management is a critical component of teaching. Students can learn and develop in a productive classroom that is well-managed. But classroom management can be difficult, particularly for inexperienced educators.

Classroom management can be approached from a different approaches, and what works for one teacher might not work for another. Nonetheless, there are some universal guidelines that might assist all educators in developing their abilities to control the classroom.

Key words: *aid, online, activity, strength, weakness, enhance, interactively, skill, learner, prediction, material, Rapport, TTT vs. STT, Seating & interaction, Monitoring, Instructions, Board work.*

a. Explain the basic principles of good classroom management.

Setting clear expectations for students is the first step towards good classroom management. Establish clear expectations for social interactions, intellectual pursuits, and academic performance. Students should be made aware of these expectations at the start of the school year, and they should be discussed and readjusted frequently. The basic principles of good classroom management, including:

1). Rapport.

Rapport is the feeling of understanding of your students. It can be showing empathy to your students when they speak about their feelings and experience. There

are many strategies teacher can establish rapport through learning the all students name and keeping eye contact, designing high quality lessons and engaging your learners and always smiling to your students can help to establish great rapport and your teaching can be effective and successful.

2). TTT vs. STT We can utilize common EFL terms like Teacher Talking Time (TTT) and Student Talking Time (STT) in EFL and ELT contexts. STT is crucial since it allows pupils to practice whatever new language they have learned. Additionally, it enables children to review and recycle existing language. Additionally, they have the option to combine and blend previously learned language with new vocabulary or structural elements. In traditional teaching TTT were in the center. Currently much more focus is given to STT.

3) Seating & interaction

The proper classroom seating arrangement is just as crucial as the curriculum, instructional strategies, and differentiated instruction. The way students are seated in the classroom may affect how well they learn. When it comes to your students' learning, reorganizing the classroom is an essential step. Different teaching methods call for different kinds of classroom arrangements. The results are quite helpful when the seating arrangement fits your teaching style, the number of students, and the size of the classroom.

The best classroom seating arrangements depend on a variety of elements, including the size and form of the room, the age range of the students, distractions, teaching methods, and the students' learning objectives. The arrangement of the seats in the classroom is a significant factor that can be used to improve the results of learners' performance. There are common seating and interactions such as student – centered way is much more common. In online classes teacher should carefully manage students when to give speech to students and careful considerations important factor.

4) Monitoring

Monitoring is a series of tasks that teachers carry out to monitor learners' performance in class. The major purposes of it are to promote instructional choices and give students feedback on how they are doing in class. In essence, this occurs when a teacher actively listens to a class as they engage in an activity. There are numerous reasons for and ways in which a teacher must monitor, and it greatly relies on the objective of the activity. Moreover, Monitoring student performance allows you to collect useful information in tracking their progress

Finally, monitoring can help your students identify who needs assistance. The instructor will be able to take the required action to assist the pupils once they have been identified as being at risk. The teacher should watch over group talks, pair projects, and team projects that involve pupils. To check on whether pupils are keeping on target, the teacher can just stroll around and listen to them. If students are not focused on the task, the teacher may utilize several classroom control strategies.

5) Instructions:

Next, you need to talk about how we might give instructions in the classroom. How do we give instructions? What can we do to ensure that learners understand instructions clearly?

Too frequently, teachers' unclear directions prevent students from participating in language learning activities in the classroom, because the students don't grasp the material. Giving clear instructions using English and engage students to participate in communicative learning tasks are important.

Teacher should give instructions step by step if it needed it is a great way to do modeling strategy then the instruction will become clear to student. Sometimes writing the steps of complicated instructions on the blackboard or whiteboard can be supportive for learners. For achieving giving clear instructions teachers should write and practice effective teacher talk for the lessons. Simplicity in giving instructions important.

6) Board work

The Classroom board or online board your screen and your slides are a key component and they serve to enhance the learning and teaching process. Students need a good, accurate written record of new topic highlighting points and the board work plays crucial part.

Teachers use the board to present a new language, to record new vocabulary, to brainstorm the ideas, writing keywords from the content, encouraging interaction by asking students to come up to the board, playing board race, "Fly swatter" game for finding the new vocabulary, to score the points in Kahoot Quiz game, In virtual board students can do almost everything that we can do on class board, presenting new material, using collaborative tools of the zoom whiteboard, inserting some emoji's and playing interactive games which enhance learning performance of students and can provide a great stimuli for learners.

List of used literature.

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